

Synthesis of Indan Derivatives as Possible Antihypertensive Agents—Part II

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1-[2-[N-methyl-N-(ω -aroyloxyalkyl)] aminoethyl] indans and 1-[2-[N-methyl-N-(ω -aroyloxyalkyl)] aminoethyl]-6-methoxyindans have been synthesised and screened pharmacologically for their antihypertensive activity. Five compounds amongst these two groups have shown appreciable activity including one whose potency is highly significant even at a dose level of 2 mg/Kg i.v.

In a previous communication¹, we reported the synthesis and pharmacology of some derivatives of 1-methyl-2-aminomethylindans as the possible antihypertensive agents. Three compounds exhibited appreciable blood pressure lowering property. This provided an impetus to synthesise the derivatives of 1-(2-aminoethyl) indans (I) which could be regarded as being structurally related to part of the reserpine molecule, in which the indole moiety has been replaced by the indan ring and to examine their hypotensive property. The indans may be considered as the isosteres of the indoles.

The synthetic route for the compounds of the type I is as shown below :

The synthesis and preliminary pharmacological data of this new type of compounds (I) have been reported herein.

$n=1, 2, 3$; $X=\text{H, OMe}$;
 $\text{Ar}=\text{Ph}$; 3, 4, 5-trimethoxyphenyl or 2-phenylvinyl.

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Pharmacology

All the compounds synthesised were screened pharmacologically for their respective hypotensive effects in the same way as described earlier¹. Histamine has been used as a standard at a dose level of 0.1 γ /Kg. The data have been shown in the Tables 2 and 4.

The acute toxicity and gross behavioural effects of the compound Nos. 4 and 5 in Table 4 were studied in mice by intraperitoneal administration of graded doses using six mice for each dose. The LD₅₀ of these two compounds have been found to be 200 and 180 mg/Kg respectively. These two compounds have no depressant action.

Experimental

All the melting points and boiling points are uncorrected.

 β -(*m*-Methoxyphenyl)glutaric acid (A ; X=OMe) :

Ethyl *m*-methoxycinnamate (106 g), ethyl malonate (120 g) and metallic sodium (3.5 g) were made to react and the product isolated in the usual way². The compound boiled at 180-81°/1.5 mm, yield 70% (160 g). The ester (160 g) so formed was hydrolysed with alcoholic sodium hydroxide and the acid was regenerated by treatment with concentrated hydrochloric acid as usual². The acid crystallised from EtOAc-benzene, m.p. 122-23°, yield 80% (80 g).

Found : C, 60.4 ; H, 5.9 ; C₁₂H₁₄O₅ requires C, 60.5 ; H, 5.88%.

6-Methoxy-3-oxo-indan-1-ylacetic acid (B ; X=OMe) :

The acid (A ; X=OMe, 70 g) was added gradually to PPA (700 g) at 30° under stirring. The mixture was stirred at 70° for 2 hr and poured into ice-cold water under vigorous stirring. The separated solid was filtered off, washed with water and crystallised from boiling water after charcoalisation, m.p. 148°, yield 85% (55 g).

Found : C, 65.32 ; H, 5.56 ; C₁₂H₁₂O₄ requires C, 65.45 ; H, 5.45%.

1-Indanylacetic acid (C ; X=H) :

The compound was prepared in 90% yield, m.p. 57° (Lit.⁴56-57°) :

6-Methoxy-1-indanylacetic acid (C ; X=OMe) :

The acid (B ; X=OMe, 55 g) was subjected to Clemmensen reduction and the product was isolated in the usual way². The compound was crystallised from pet. ether (60-80°)-benzene ; m.p. 85° ; yield 88% (45 g).

Found : C, 70.1 ; H, 6.7 ; C₁₂H₁₄O₃ requires C, 69.9 ; H, 6.8%.

1-Indanyl-(*N*-methyl)acetamide (D ; X=H) :

The acid (C ; X=H, 60 g) was converted to its acid chloride by reaction with thionyl chloride

(100 ml) in presence of dry benzene (250 ml) at 40-45°. The product was distilled at 126°/2 mm. The chloride diluted with dry benzene was added dropwise to a cooled mixture of methylamine (75 ml, 30%) and sodium hydroxide solution (20 ml, 2*N*). The mixture was stirred for 4 hr at 15°. The product was extracted with benzene and isolated by distillation ; b.p. 182°/1.0 mm ; m.p. 65-66° ; yield 65% (42 g). The purity of the compound was checked by the tlc on silica gel with EtOAc-benzene (1 : 4), Rf 0.68. Ir (Nujol) 3300 (NH), 1685 cm⁻¹(C=O), nmr (CDCl₃, TMS) δ 7.08 (s, 4H, aromatic H), 5.85 (broad singlet, H, -NHCO-), 2.7-3.5 (m, 5H, C-1H, C-3H₂ and -CH₂-CO-), 2.62 (d, 3H, N-CH₃), 1.3-2.1 ppm (discontinuous multiplet, 4H, C-2H₂ and -CH₂-).

Found : C, 76.4 ; H, 8.1 ; N, 7.3 ; C₁₂H₁₆NO requires C, 76.2 ; H, 7.93 ; N, 7.4%.

6-Methoxy-1-indanyl-(*N*-methyl)acetamide (D ; X=OMe) :

The acid (C ; X=OMe, 34 g) was converted to its chloride by reaction with thionyl chloride (50 ml) as usual. But the later could not be distilled. The crude acid chloride diluted with dry benzene was made to react with methylamine solution (40 ml, 30%) in presence of sodium hydroxide solution (20 ml, 2*N*). The yellowish solid was filtered off and crystallised from benzene-pet. ether (60-80°). Colorless, shining, needle-shaped crystals, m.p. 91-92° were obtained in 67% yield (25 g). Tlc showed one single spot on silica gel with EtOAc-benzene (1 : 4) at an Rf of 0.61. Ir (Nujol) 3300 (NH), 1690 cm⁻¹(C=O), nmr (CDCl₃, TMS) δ 6.85-7.25 (m, 3H, aromatic H), 5.85 (broad singlet, H, -NHCO-), 3.8 (s, 3H, -OCH₃) 2.8-3.4 (m, 5H, C-1H, C-3H₂ and -CH₂CO-), 2.62 (d, 3H, N-CH₃), 1.3-2.1 ppm (discontinuous multiplet, 4H, C-2H₂ and -CH₂-).

Found : C, 71.3 ; H, 7.7 ; N, 6.5 ; C₁₃H₁₇NO₂ requires C, 71.2 ; H, 7.76 ; N, 6.4%.

1-(2-*N*-Methylaminoethyl) indan (E ; X=H)

The amide (D ; X=H, 20 g) was reduced with LAH (5.0 g) in tetrahydrofuran (300 ml) under reflux for 60 hr. Excess LAH was decomposed and the amine was extracted with ether. The solvent was distilled off and the residue was dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid. The solution was made ammoniacal and the liberated base was extracted with ether. The ether solution was washed with water dried (Na₂SO₄) and the solvent removed. The residual liquid was distilled, b.p. 100-102°/1.0 mm, yield 75% (14 g). Ir (film) 3380 cm⁻¹(NH). Tlc on silica gel with EtOAc-pet. ether (60-80°, 1 : 4) showed one single spot, Rf 0.77.

Found : C, 82.34 ; H, 9.6 ; N, 7.92 ; C₁₂H₁₇N requires C, 82.3 ; H, 9.7 ; N, 8.0%.

The hydrochloride was crystallised from benzene-pet. ether (60-80°) mixture, m.p. 185-86°.

1-[(2*N*-methylaminoethyl)-6-methoxyindan (*E*; *X* = OMe) :

The amide (*D* *X* = OMe, 25 g) was reduced with LAH (6.0 g) in tetrahydrofuran (300 ml) and the amine was isolated in the usual way; b.p. 148-49°/0.8 mm; yield 80% (18 g). Tlc on silica gel with EtOAc-pet. ether (60-80°, 1 : 4) showed only one spot, Rf 0.70. Ir (film) 3380 cm⁻¹(NH).

Found : C, 75.92 ; H, 9.30 ; N, 6.80 ; C₁₃H₁₉NO requires C, 76.0 ; H, 9.27 ; N, 6.83%.

The hydrochloride crystallised from benzene-pet. ether (60-80°) mixture in colorless needles, m.p. 202°.

1-[2-[*N*-Methyl-*N*-(2-hydroxyethyl)] aminoethyl] indan (*F*; *X* = H) :

The amine (*E*, *X* = H, 5 g) was made to react with ethylene oxide (5 ml) at -5 to 0° for 5 hr. Excess ethylene oxide was evaporated. The compound was recovered by distillation; b.p. 170-71°/1.0 mm; yield 90% (5.6 g). Tlc on silica gel with EtOAc-pet. ether (60-80°) showed one single spot, Rf 0.82. Ir (film) 3400 cm⁻¹ (-OH).

Found : C, 76.6 ; H, 9.65 ; N, 6.38 ; C₁₄H₂₁NO requires C, 76.7 ; H, 9.6 ; N, 6.4%.

1-[2-[*N*-Methyl-*N*-(2-hydroxyethyl)] aminoethyl]-5-methoxyindan (*F*; *X* = OMe) :

The amine (*E*; *X* = OMe, 5.0 g) was allowed to react with ethylene oxide (5 ml) at -5 to 0° for 5 hr and the product was isolated as usual. B.P. 205°/0.8 mm; yield 95% (5.7 g). Tlc showed one single spot on silica gel with EtOAc-benzene (1 : 4) at an Rf of 0.75. Ir (film) 3400 cm⁻¹ (-OH).

1-[2-(*N*-Methyl-*N*-(2-aryloxyethyl)] aminoethyl]-indans (*I*; *X* = H and OMe, *n* = 1; *Ar* = Ph; 3, 4, 5-(OMe)₃-C₆H₂; -CH=CH-Ph) :

The *N*-substituted aminoethanol (*F*; *X* = H or OMe; 0.1 mole) in dry benzene (0.2 mole) and dry pyridine (0.1 mole) was refluxed with an appropriate acid chloride (0.125 mole) for 4 hrs. In case of the cinnamyl chloride, the reaction mixture was stirred at room temp. for 4 hr. Excess pyridine was removed with dilute hydrochloric acid and the benzene solution was washed with water and dried (Na₂SO₄). Benzene was removed and the end-products were collected by distillation. The purity of the tertiary amines formed was checked by the tlc on silica-gel, and the structures were confirmed by Ir spectra.

1-[2-[*N*-Methyl-*N*-(*ω*-aryloxyalkyl)] aminoethyl] indans (*I*; *n* = 2 and 3; *X* = H and OMe; *Ar* = Ph; 3, 4, 5-(OMe)₃-C₆H₂; -CH=CH=Ph) :

The secondary amine (*E*; *X* = H or OMe; 0.1 mole) in dry xylene (0.2 mole) was refluxed with an appropriate chloroester (0.15 mole) and K₂CO₃ (0.1 mole) at 140-150° in a nitrogen atmosphere for 20 hr. The solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure and the product was extracted with dry ether. The amine hydrochlorides were precipitated out with ethereal hydrogen chloride and dissolved in water. The aqueous solution was made ammoniacal, and, the liberated amines were extracted with benzene. The benzene extract was washed with water, dried (Na₂SO₄) and the solvent was removed. From the residual liquid, the end-product was isolated by distillation under reduced pressure. The purity of the products were checked by the tlc. The IR spectra of the compounds agree well with the expected structures. The physical and analytical data are recorded in the Tables 1 and 3.

TABLE 1—DATA OF 1-[2-[*N*-METHYL-*N*-(*ω*-AROXYALKYL)] AMINOETHYL] INDANS (*I*, *X* = H)

Sl. No.	<i>n</i>	<i>Ar</i>	B.P. °C/mm	Yield	Molecular Formula	Analysis %			Rf*	I.R. cm ⁻¹ (film)	HCl** m.p. °C
						C	H	N			
1	1	Ph	180-81/0.8	89	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ O ₂ N	Found 78.2 calc. 78.02	7.7 7.74	4.3 4.38	0.72	1720	121-22
2	1	3,4,5-(OMe) ₃ -C ₆ H ₂	165/1.5	58	C ₂₄ H ₃₁ O ₅ N	Found 69.8 calc. 69.75	7.6 7.5	3.4 3.99	0.70	1710	132
3	1	-CH=OH-Ph	245/1.0	38	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ O ₂ N	Found 79.1 calc. 79.08	7.8 7.73	4.1 4.0	0.74	1710	127-28
4	2	Ph	205/1.0	50	C ₂₂ H ₂₇ O ₂ N	Found 78.2 calc. 78.34	8.1 8.01	4.2 4.15	0.75	1720	135-37
5	2	3,4,5-(OMe) ₃ -C ₆ H ₂	240/0.6	47	C ₂₅ H ₃₃ O ₅ N	Found 70.3 calc. 70.25	7.7 7.73	3.3 3.28	0.73	1710	142-43
6	2	-CH=CH-Ph	145/1.5	57	C ₂₄ H ₂₉ O ₂ N	Found 79.5 calc. 79.34	8.1 7.98	3.8 3.85	0.68	1710	156-57
7	3	Ph	150/0.6	25	C ₂₃ H ₂₉ O ₂ N	Found 78.6 calc. 78.78	8.2 8.14	4.1 3.98	0.69	1720	151
8	3	3,4,5-(OMe) ₃ -C ₆ H ₂	154/1.0	28	C ₂₆ H ₃₅ O ₅ N	Found 70.8 calc. 70.74	7.8 7.93	3.2 3.17	0.65	1710	180
9	3	-CH=CH-Ph	130/1.0	25	C ₂₅ H ₃₁ O ₂ N	Found 79.6 calc. 79.57	8.3 8.22	3.6 3.71	0.71	1710	183

* Solvent system : EtOAc-pet. ether (60°-80°) 1 : 4 (v/v).

** Crystallised from EtOAc-benzene.

TABLE 2—PHARMACOLOGICAL DATA OF COMPOUND I, X=H

Sl. No.	n	Ar	Dose (mg/Kg) iv	Fall in blood pressure* (mm Hg)	Remarks
1	1	Ph	5	8 ± 2.2	Inactive compound
2	1	3,4,5-(OMe) ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	5	10 ± 2.5	Inactive compound
3	1	-CH=CH-Ph	5	6 ± 1.8	Inactive compound
4	2	Ph	5	20 ± 2.2	Transient effect
5	2	3,4,5-(OMe) ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	5	18 ± 2.4	Transient effect
6	2	-CH=CH-Ph	5	14 ± 3.1	Inactive compound
7	3	Ph	5	16 ± 2.7	Transient effect
8	3	3,4,5-(OMe) ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	5	18 ± 2.6	Transient effect
9	3	-CH=CH-Ph	5	12 ± 1.8	Inactive compound
10		Histamine	0.17/Kg	20 ± 1.6	Control

* Data on six normotensive anaesthetised cats.

TABLE 3—DATA OF 1-[2-[N-METHYL-N-(ω-AROYLOXYALKYL)] AMINOETHYL]-6-METHOXYINDANS (I, X=OMe)

Sl. No.	n	Ar	B.P.°C/mm	Yield %	Molecular Formula	Analysis %			Rf*	I.R. cm ⁻¹ (film) C=O	HCl** m.p.°C
						C	H	N			
1	1	Ph	190/0.6	93	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ O ₃ N	Found 74.9 calc. 74.8	7.5 7.64	4.0 3.96	0.74	1710	181
2	1	3,4,5-(OMe) ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	190/1.5	45	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ O ₆ N	Found 67.6 calc. 67.7	7.4 7.45	3.2 3.16	0.70	1710	145
3	1	-CH=CH-Ph	250/0.6	60	C ₂₄ H ₂₅ O ₃ N	Found 75.8 calc. 76.0	7.7 7.65	3.6 3.7	0.72	1720	140-41
4	2	Ph	228/1.0	34	C ₂₃ H ₂₅ O ₃ N	Found 75.3 calc. 75.2	7.8 7.9	3.7 3.8	0.75	1720	154
5	2	3,4,5-(OMe) ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	270/0.4	45	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ O ₆ N	Found 68.4 calc. 68.27	7.8 7.65	3.1 3.06	0.69	1710	167
6	2	-CH=CH-Ph	255/0.8	55	C ₂₅ H ₂₁ O ₃ N	Found 76.1 calc. 76.3	7.9 7.96	3.6 3.56	0.67	1720	160-62
7	3	Ph	160/1.5	33	C ₂₄ H ₂₇ O ₃ N	Found 75.5 calc. 75.6	8.1 8.13	3.6 3.67	0.71	1710	172
8	3	3,4,5-(OMe) ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	170/0.8	25	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ O ₆ N	Found 68.9 calc. 68.8	7.8 7.85	3.0 2.97	0.65	1710	194
9	3	-CH=CH-Ph	155/1.5	25	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ O ₃ N	Found 76.5 calc. 76.65	8.2 8.1	3.5 3.44	0.68	1720	168

* Solvent system : EtOAc-pet.ether (60°-80°) 1 : 4 (v/v).

** Crystallised from EtOAc-benzene.

TABLE 4—PHARMACOLOGICAL DATA OF COMPOUND I, X=OMe

Sl. No.	n	Ar	Dose (mg/Kg) iv	Fall in blood pressure* (mm Hg)	Remarks
1	1	Ph	5	10 ± 1.9	Inactive compound
2	1	3,4,5-(OMe) ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	5	12 ± 2.1	" "
3	1	-CH=CH-Ph	5	6 ± 1.8	" "
4	2	Ph	{5 {2	{70 ± 3.2 {40 ± 3.6	Sustained action lasting for 2 hrs Highly significant activity.
5	2	3,4,5-(OMe) ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	5	36 ± 4.4	Significant activity.
6	2	-CH=CH-Ph	5	16 ± 1.7	Transient effect
7	3	Ph	5	18 ± 2.5	" "
8	3	3,4,5-(OMe) ₃ -C ₆ H ₃	5	18 ± 2.1	" "
9	3	-CH=CH-Ph	5	14 ± 2.7	" "
10		Histamine	0.1/Kg	18 ± 1.4	"Control"

* Data on six normotensive anaesthetised cats.

Discussion

It appears that among all the compounds of the general structure I which have been tested, the compound No. 4 in Table 4 is the most active one in the normotensive anaesthetised cats even at a dose of 2 mg/Kg iv. The preliminary results indicate that the two compounds No. 4 and 5 in Table 4 might attract interest as antihypertensive agents.

In this class of compounds also, activity becomes noteworthy when $n=2$. Incorporation of a methoxyl group increases the activity, while the activity is least when the aroyl group is cinnamyl in the structure I.

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